

A Study of the Recent Trends in Indian Carpet Industry and Roadmap Ahead

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Abstract:

The editorial examines the Global as well as Indian Carpet Industry. Here the discussion begins with providing the overview of the Global Carpets Industry followed by discussions on Indian carpet Industry. The study highlights on various success factors affecting acceptance of Carpets followed by weaknesses, opportunities and challenges of the carpet industry

Keywords: *Acceptance, Carpets, opportunities, threats, overview, strengths, weaknesses*

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1. Introduction

Carpet is a Floor Layer which is made completely by human hands by knotting, tufting or weaving, in which handspun Yarn of natural fibers is used with its very unique character and design. Carpets especially Handmade are works of art which bear beauty and sophistication to any space. They are fashioned by means of a variety of methods and materials, and each type of handmade carpet narrates its own story making it very exclusive in features and style. The assortment of materials and techniques used in producing these carpets is enthralling.

Carpets like other products are bearing properties which can be defined both by their physical descriptions and by their meanings as per society. Carpets have a practical value and a restrained life as the carpet may be made of any good material but each of them have a limited life. Nevertheless, a carpet is a product with a very strong social meaning. Most relevant example to this is Turkmen carpet which has a deep representational meaning ascribed to status of a newlywed and the skills and possessions that she had given at marriage. The tradition of gifting carpets at the time of marriage has remained till today as a valuable social ritual in Afghanistan.

2. Materials & Methods

The objective of the study is to provide an outline of the Global Carpet industry then shifting the focus to Indian carpet Industry. The study would also analyse the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for Indian carpet Industry. Information has been poised from various sources including books journals research papers websites for the reason of study. This study uses secondary data, with texts and modern scholarly works, to explore the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for Indian carpet Industry. A literature review involved examining journal articles, books, manuscripts, and historical records to gain insights into the industry's state. These resources have been studied to understand the industry's perspective and progression. The combination of these methods has enabled a detailed exploration and records of the Indian Carpet industry.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 History

The origin of Carpets is still considered furtive but assuredly, ruddling arrangements of floor covering clothes are present since 7000 BC. There are various narrations regarding the progression of carpets. Indian Carpet industry is oldest and legendary businesses in the world. Carpets generally are crafted through weaving, knotting, tufting, knitting, braiding, or felting. The creating of Indian Hand-crafted Carpets is considered very time utilizing and workforce demanding. Currently India is considered a centre in Southern Asia for manufacturing numerous forms of Handmade Carpets. There are several notable carpet centres in India including Rajasthan, Punjab, UP, J & K, Haryana, MP, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, etc. Each centre has a cluster

of weavers and makers of carpets. Hand-knotted carpets and rugs have a rich history in India, dating back to around 985 CE, with Mahabalipuram identified as one of the oldest production centers in the country. While some historical accounts suggest that the carpet art form originated elsewhere and was introduced to India by the Mughals from Turkey and Persia, evidence indicates that it became deeply entrenched in Indian culture during the Mughal era.

As the Mughal Empire rose to power in India, resident artisans began creating carpets for Mughal emperors, incorporating elements of Mughal and Islamic art and architecture into their designs. Carpet weaving thus became an integral part of Indian culture from that period onward. Historical records from the fourteenth century document the widespread use of carpets in cities like Daulatabad, Delhi, and Multan, reaching new heights of prominence in the sixteenth century under sustained Mughal patronage. Emperor Babar, who reigned from 1526 to 1530, played a significant role in introducing and promoting the art of carpet weaving in India. He imported carpets from Turkey and Persia, laying the foundation for the establishment and proliferation of this craft within the country. Mughal emperors actively engaged artisans to produce elaborate carpets for their palaces and courts. These Mughal carpets were renowned for their vibrant colors, opulent use of gold and silk threads, and intricate designs, showcasing the artistic brilliance of the era.

In 1851, handmade carpets received significant acclaim in Indian history for their exceptional quality, designs, weave, and color palette at the prestigious London exhibition. Following the British colonial period, the carpet industry experienced a resurgence in various regions of India, marked by variations in designs, colors, quality, weaving methods, and materials used. Over time, carpet weaving proliferated across the Indian subcontinent, with different regions developing their unique styles and techniques, contributing to the rich tapestry of Indian carpet craftsmanship.

3.2 Theoretical Background

The presence of small and medium-sized exporters with substantial export capacity, alongside skilled weavers capable of crafting intricate and unique floor covering designs, is the primary strengths of Indian carpet production [1].

16 carpet manufacturers in Jaipur were examined in a study, with each zone consisting of four randomly selected units. The research revealed consistent tools and processes across all areas involved in hand-knotted carpet production. Highlighting the industry's significance, the findings underscored its role in meeting foreign exchange requirements and providing employment opportunities. The study emphasized the necessity for professionally trained, well-equipped, and informed designer clippers, finishers, and production managers within the industry [2].

The carpet industry not only offers employment opportunities for educated and skilled women but also for semi-skilled women, thus empowering them [3].

A study highlighted carpet weaving as a major cottage industry in India, employing thousands of village artisans and making substantial contributions to the economy through both balance of payments and employment generation [4].

A study on Carpets explored the multifaceted uses of carpets, whether as floor coverings or decorative items. The research concluded that handmade carpets offer healthier usage compared to machine-made ones [5]. There has been a decline in demand for handmade carpets in the international market due to consumer preferences shifting towards cheaper, less durable, and modern designs over traditional, costlier options [6]. 4P's are essential for the Indian Carpet Business. These tools play a crucial role in devising future strategies and enhancing sustainability within the market. It was further observed that while traditional markets may have reached saturation points, new markets present opportunities for growth [7].

There has been an emphasis upon the Carpet sector's prominence due to its low capital investment requirement and substantial export prospective [8].

In 2014, the economic growth potential of handicrafts was highlighted, with a suggestion to organize artisans into cooperatives to enhance the marketing of their products [9].

In 2012, it was analysed that the majority (90%) of carpet weaving occurred in households using family labour, with only a small portion (10%) operated by hired workers in factories. Many factories were observed to be small-

scale, owned by individuals with limited resources, and employing only a few workers, including children. This socio-economic structure positioned individual weavers at the base, with exporters and major manufacturers often separated from them by layers of intermediaries [10].

3.3 Size of the Global Carpet Industry

As per latest market investigation piloted, the global Carpet market is poised to achieve a CAGR of 4.6% from 2023 to 2032. In 2022, the market size is projected to reach USD 64.99 billion, with an anticipated valuation of USD 97.41 billion by 2032 [11].

The carpet market encompasses the manufacturing, distribution, and sale of carpets, rugs, and other flooring products. It includes a wide range of carpet types, such as tufted, woven, needle-felt, and knotted carpets, along with carpet tiles and area rugs. These products find applications in both residential and commercial settings, driven by factors such as aesthetics, comfort, insulation, acoustics, and safety.

As a significant segment of the global flooring industry, the carpet market is influenced by various factors, including economic conditions, trends in interior design, technological advancements, and environmental considerations. As per The Brainy Insights, the size of the carpet market was valued at USD 72.39 billion in 2023 to USD 110.82 billion by 2033 [12].

3.4 Growth of the Indian Carpet Industry

Figure 1: Growth of Carpet Industry from 2015-19 as per report from Mordor Intelligence

India at this time is a leader in creating handmade carpets may it be the volume or value. The glory of Indian handmade carpets is acknowledged worldwide because of its distinguishable share in the global exports. The volume of exports is as high as 90% of the total production. Throughout April-November 2019, hand-crafted carpets exported from India was USD 916.15 million. Just USA only has 48.84% share out of total export of INR. 10207.91 Crores in 2018-19. 27.25% of the Indian carpet exports are steered to Europe [13].

The Indian government has made significant strides in fostering the development of the carpet industry. Carpet Export Promotion Council was instituted in 1982 under the Ministry of Textiles, Government of India for research, development, and quality assurance within the sector. Additionally, the Indian Institute of Carpet Technology (IICT) was inaugurated by the Ministry of Textiles in 2001, aimed at cultivating skilled professionals and fostering design innovation within the carpet industry. Despite these initiatives, the industry's growth remains hindered. Research by Das et al. highlights the industry's struggle with innovation and outdated technology, leading to a significant portion of carpet weavers seeking opportunities in other sectors. Despite its global prominence, the Indian carpet industry grapples with various challenges. Das et al. underscore issues such as low wages, exploitation of labor, limited job opportunities, minimal job security, and the pervasive influence of intermediaries as major obstacles confronting the industry [14].

India plays a pivotal role in the global carpet market, with a remarkable 90% of the country's rug production being exported. In the period of April-November 2019 alone, India exported handmade rugs worth INR 64,407.19 crore (USD 916.15 million). Renowned for its expertise and heritage in handmade rugs, India leads in both volume and value of production, boasting a significant share in global exports. These rugs reach over 70 countries worldwide, with major importers including UK, USA, Germany, Canada, Australia, South Africa, Europe etc. The evolving dynamics of globalization present new opportunities for the burgeoning Indian carpet market. India's Carpet &

Rugs Market is projected to reach USD 7.13 Bn by 2028, growing at a CAGR of 6.15% as per Research & Markets [15].

Figure 2: Market Forecast of Indian Carpet & Rug Industry as per report from Research & Markets

Figure 3: Predicted Growth of Carpet Industry from 2014-29 as per report from Mordor Intelligence

3.5 Problems of carpet industry

There are several problems currently faced by the Indian carpet Industry.

- There has been an upsurge in the cost of raw materials. Studies show that cost of raw materials have emerged by about 50% in recent years. Also, downgrading of rupee has increased the cost of bring in raw materials.
- Deficiency of skilled work force is the next issue. It is very relevant to mention that artisans are not paid well, and conversely not everyone is interested to pay more for buying hand crafted products so people are moving towards buying machine made products. Also, most weavers are largely cultivators, working as crafts worker during the lean agrarian months.
- There is a strong global Competition and Indian carpets face tough competition from nations like Iran, China and Nepal. Iran accounts for approx. 25% of exports, China about 20% and Nepal about 10% [18].
- There has been a lot of possibility for strengthening Exports of Indian Handmade Carpets but Indian Carpet industry sees lack of quality infrastructure due to political indifferences and to marginal investing in R and D which lacks supervising system which is required to evaluate the development of projects.
- Though all efforts are being done to promote Indian carpets in international market but then there has been dissention involving task of CEPC in providing platform to Indian Carpets at global levels.

- Lack of Infrastructure-Government has put in a lot of efforts by initiating various schemes but most of the initiatives have really not worked very well due to lack of development in power, roads and drinking water there is a strong need to develop banking facilities so that the industry can reach its full potential.

3.6 Growth trends

Carpet weaving in India is deeply rooted in tradition, tracing back to 16th-century Persian influences. Typically hand-knotted, Indian rugs feature diverse and intricate arrangements in designs. The country's carpet business primarily thrives as rustic, labour-concentrated cottage industry.

Indian silk Carpets & rugs stand out for their originality, vibrant colors, superior quality, captivating designs, and long-lasting durability. However, there's a noticeable shift in demand towards tufted rugs, driven by the affordability of synthetic materials and reduced labour requirements in their production. International consumers are increasingly favouring washable and budget-friendly rug options, reflecting evolving preferences in the global market.

The carpet market has witnessed notable growth trends in recent years, characterized by the following key developments:

- **Surge in Demand for Eco-Friendly Carpets:** There is a notable uptick in the demand for carpets crafted from sustainable and recyclable materials. Increasing environmental consciousness among consumers is driving the preference for eco-friendly carpet options. The manufacturers are engaged in a lot of Research and development to create innovative and sustainable Carpets. The adoption of eco-friendly materials is another key aspect of sustainable manufacturing. Traditional manufacturing processes often rely on materials that are harmful to the environment, such as plastics derived from fossil fuels or metals mined through destructive practices. However, there is a growing trend towards using renewable and biodegradable materials, such as bamboo, recycled plastics, and organic cotton. These materials offer comparable performance to their conventional counterparts while significantly reducing environmental impact
- **Expansion of the Construction Industry:** The burgeoning construction sector, especially in developing nations, has fueled heightened demand for carpets in both commercial and residential constructions .
- **Technological Advancements:** Ongoing advancements in carpet manufacturing technology have paved the way for the production of high-performance carpets boasting enhanced durability, stain resistance, and ease of maintenance.
- **Augmented focus on Design and Aesthetics:** Design and aesthetic appeal have become paramount in the carpet industry, particularly in residential settings. Consumers are actively seeking carpets that can elevate the visual allure of their living spaces and harmonize with their interior décor. The Carpet Industry also follows the Trend Predictions to Design and create Carpets which are structurally, functionally and aesthetically strong .
- **Rise in Renovation and Remodeling Projects:** With more individuals opting to stay in their residences and undertaking home upgrades, there has been a noticeable increase in the demand for carpets in renovation and remodeling endeavors.
- **Emergence of Online Sales and Distribution:** The proliferation of e-commerce platforms has revolutionized the carpet market, enabling customers to conveniently purchase carpets online. This trend has facilitated greater accessibility to a diverse range of products and enhanced price comparison opportunities for consumers [16].
- **Sustainable manufacturing practices, resource conservation, and the adoption of eco-friendly materials:** these are crucial components of building a more environmentally responsible industrial sector. As the global population continues to grow, the pressure on natural resources intensifies, making it imperative for industries to embrace sustainable approaches that minimize their ecological footprint. One of the cornerstones of sustainable manufacturing is the efficient use of resources. This involves optimizing production processes to reduce waste generation, energy consumption, and water usage. Implementing techniques like lean manufacturing, which focuses on eliminating waste and maximizing efficiency, can significantly reduce resource consumption while improving productivity. Additionally, recycling and reuse play vital roles in resource conservation. Industries can adopt closed-loop systems where materials are recycled and reused within the production process, minimizing the need for virgin resources. By implementing comprehensive recycling programs and designing products for easy disassembly and recycling, manufacturers can reduce the demand for raw materials and decrease the amount of waste sent to landfills.

3.7 Opportunities ahead

The carpet market presents numerous significant opportunities for growth and advancement. Here are some key areas of opportunity:

- **Diversification of Product Offerings:** Manufacturers can explore opportunities to diversify their product range by venturing into luxury carpets, eco-friendly options, and customized solutions tailored for both commercial and residential applications.
- **Technological Innovation:** Continuous investment in research and development to introduce innovative carpets with enhanced performance and eco-friendly features can help manufacturers gain a competitive edge in the market.
- **Partnerships and Collaborations:** Collaborations among carpet manufacturers, architects, designers, and contractors can stimulate demand for carpets in construction and renovation projects, driving growth opportunities.
- **Sustainability:** With an increasing demand for sustainable products, there is an opportunity for manufacturers to invest in environmentally friendly production methods and materials, and market their carpets as eco-friendly solutions.
- **Online Sales and Marketing:** Leveraging the growing trend of online sales and marketing, manufacturers can expand their reach and increase sales through e-commerce platforms and social media channels.
- The carpet market is confronted with several significant threats that may jeopardize its growth and profitability.

3.8 Key concerns of the Carpet Industry

- **Competition from Alternative Flooring Options:** Carpets encounter competition from various other flooring alternatives, such as hardwood, vinyl, and tile, which may offer similar or superior performance at comparable prices as their producers are also in the process of R & D to fight the competition.
- **Economic Downturns:** Economic downturns have the potential to impact consumer spending on carpets, particularly within the residential sector, where purchases are often discretionary and subject to economic fluctuations.
- **Environmental Concerns:** Increasing awareness regarding the environmental impact of carpets, including non-biodegradable materials and chemicals used in production and disposal, may lead to heightened regulations and consumer preferences shifting towards more eco-friendly flooring options.
- **Disruptive Technologies:** The emergence of disruptive technologies like 3D printing and digital printing could revolutionize carpet manufacturing methods, potentially altering consumer preferences and favoring newer, more innovative products.
- **Raw Material Price Fluctuations:** Fluctuations in the prices of raw materials, such as synthetic fibers and natural fibers like wool, can significantly impact the production costs of carpets, thereby affecting profit margins within the industry.
- **Changing Consumer Preferences:** Shifting consumer preferences in flooring materials and designs, influenced by evolving trends in interior design and lifestyle choices, have the potential to disrupt demand for carpets and reshape market dynamics.
- **Market Saturation:** Some regions may experience market saturation with numerous existing carpet installations, limiting new sales and growth opportunities, particularly in mature markets.
- **Competition from Alternative Flooring:** Carpets face competition from alternative flooring options such as hardwood, laminate, vinyl, and tiles. Consumer preferences for these alternatives, driven by ease of maintenance and changing design trends, pose a challenge to the carpet market.

3.9 Opportunities ahead in the Indian Carpet Industry

- **Surge in Demand for Sustainable Products:** Increasing environmental awareness creates opportunities for the carpet market to develop and promote sustainable, eco-friendly products. Manufacturers can focus on utilizing recycled materials, reducing carbon footprints, and adopting environmentally friendly production processes. India has a rich heritage and history in sustainability.
- **Innovation in Materials and Technology:** Investments in research and development can lead to innovations in carpet materials and technology. This includes the development of stain-resistant, durable, and low-maintenance carpets that align with evolving consumer preferences.
- **Customization and Personalization Trends:** Consumer demand for personalized flooring options presents an opportunity for the carpet market to offer customizable products. This includes a variety of colors, textures, and designs that cater to individual preferences and interior design trends.

3.10 Challenges for Indian Carpet Industry

- Maintenance and Cleanliness Concerns: Carpets require regular maintenance, and concerns about cleanliness, allergens, and the accumulation of dust and debris can deter some consumers. Addressing these challenges involves developing and promoting easy-to-maintain and hygienic carpet solutions.
- Global Trade Uncertainties: Trade tensions, tariffs, and uncertainties in global trade relations can impact the carpet market. Changes in trade policies may disrupt supply chains, influence production costs, and affect the competitiveness of carpet products in the international market.
- Strong Global competition from USA

4. Conclusion

To bolster the global market share of carpets, particularly hand-knotted varieties, it is essential to optimize pertinent processes. This enhancement will not only benefit the industry's socio-economic standing but also uplift the artisan community. To achieve this objective, it is imperative to engage in Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) initiatives and/or receive interventions from the national government. As per report by Freedonia, The global demand for carpets and rugs is projected to grow at a rate of 2.3% annually, reaching 5.4 billion square meters by 2027, with a total market value of \$63.7 billion [17]. This growth will be fueled by several factors, including:

1. Increased construction activity in both residential and nonresidential sectors, particularly in regions such as Asia/Pacific and Africa/Mideast.
2. The increasing popularity of carpet tiles in non-residential buildings is driven by their convenient installation and replacement.

4.1 Future trends in Global Carpet & Rug Demand

Through 2027, global demand for carpets and rugs is forecast to increase 2.3% annually to 5.4 billion square meters as per report by Freedonia [19]. Growth in the rug market is projected to greatly outpace that of the carpet market, primarily due to continued market inroads made by luxury vinyl tile in the US and Europe, which is taking substantial share away from wall-to-wall carpeting in the world's largest markets for carpet hard surface flooring gaining market share worldwide, which increases the likelihood of accent and decorative rugs to cover portions of the existing floor covering product.

Source: The Freedonia Group

Figure 4. Global carpet & Rug Demand by Product 2000-32 (million Sq. Mtrs.) as per report by Freedonia [20]

Figure 5. Global carpet & Rug Demand by Region 2000-32 (million Sq. Mtrs.) as per report by Freedonia [21]

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